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EMPLOYER BRANDING IN UZBEKISTAN: HOW TO BECOME AN EMPLOYER OF CHOICE FOR TALENT

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Abstract. The article examines employer branding as a strategic tool for attracting and retaining talent in Uzbekistan's rapidly transforming labour market. It clarifies the concepts of employer brand and employee value proposition (EVP) and reviews the key academic and applied frameworks in this field. Drawing on national labour-market statistics and a survey of companies operating in Uzbekistan, the study identifies the principal drivers of employer attractiveness and the main barriers faced by local organisations. On this basis, the article proposes a practical model for building an authentic employer brand and offers recommendations for companies and policymakers aimed at transforming the country's demographic dividend into a sustainable competitive advantage.

Keywords: employer branding, employee value proposition (EVP), talent attraction, talent retention, human capital, HR strategy, employer of choice, Uzbekistan.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается HR-брендинг как стратегический инструмент привлечения и удержания талантов на быстро трансформирующемся рынке труда Узбекистана. Уточняются понятия бренда работодателя и ценностного предложения работодателя (EVP). На основе национальной статистики и опроса компаний, действующих в Узбекистане, выявлены ключевые факторы привлекательности работодателя и основные барьеры, с которыми сталкиваются местные организации. На этой основе предложена практическая модель построения HR-бренда.

Ключевые слова: HR-брендинг, ценностное предложение работодателя, привлечение талантов, удержание персонала, человеческий капитал, HR-стратегия, работодатель мечты, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

In a knowledge-driven economy, an organisation's ability to attract, engage, and retain skilled employees has become at least as important as its access to capital or technology. As competition for qualified specialists intensifies, the concept of employer branding — the deliberate management of an organisation's reputation as a place to work — has moved from the margins of human resource practice to the centre of corporate strategy. For Uzbekistan, this issue is particularly relevant. The country combines one of the youngest populations in the region with a fast-growing, reform-driven economy, which makes the competition for talent both a strategic opportunity and a structural challenge.

This article aims to examine employer branding as a strategic mechanism for talent attraction and retention in Uzbekistan, identify the factors that make an employer attractive in the national context, and propose practical recommendations for organisations seeking to become employers of choice for talent.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the past five years, employer branding has become one of the most actively researched areas in human resource management, reflecting the intensifying global competition for skilled labour. Contemporary scholarship defines the employer brand as the deliberate management of an organisation's reputation as a place to work and conceptualises employer branding as a strategic process that includes developing a value proposition, communicating it externally to attract candidates, and reinforcing it internally to engage and retain employees [1; 2].

Digital transformation has reshaped how this process functions in practice. Research on post-Soviet and other emerging markets shows that social media has become a primary channel through which organisations project their employer image and candidates verify it. As a result, an authentic online presence and an engaging, gamified candidate experience now strongly influence applicants' intention to apply and overall recruitment performance [3; 4].

At the heart of every employer brand lies the employee value proposition (EVP), which represents the combination of economic, developmental, social, and psychological benefits an organisation offers in exchange for the skills and commitment of its employees. Both applied and academic studies regard a clear and credible EVP as the core of the employer brand and the strongest driver of employer attractiveness. At the same

time, the employer brand also includes visual identity, communication messages, and the lived experience of candidates and employees [3; 7].

Since young people now constitute a significant share of new entrants to the labour market, a growing body of research focuses on Generation Z. Existing studies show that these candidates prioritise meaningful work, learning and development opportunities, flexibility, work–life balance, and authentic, values-driven employers over salary alone [5; 6]. In the post-Soviet and Central Asian context, the academic literature remains comparatively limited, although national scholars increasingly link human capital development with the modernisation of education and digitalisation [8].

Taken together, recent studies show that a strong employer brand is based on an authentic and well-communicated EVP, is increasingly delivered through digital channels, and is adapted to the expectations of younger talent. It also produces economically significant effects, including lower employee turnover, higher engagement, and reduced recruitment costs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study relies on a combination of general scientific and applied methods. A systemic approach is used to examine the employer brand as a set of interrelated elements, including compensation, professional development, work environment, organisational purpose, and reputation, rather than as an isolated communication activity.

Empirically, the article draws on secondary data, including official labour market statistics of Uzbekistan published by the Statistics Agency and the Ministry of Employment and Poverty Reduction, World Bank human capital indicators, and the findings of an industry survey of companies operating in the country, namely the EY Salary and Compensation Review 2024/2025, which covers 60 firms across different sectors.

Methods of comparative analysis, grouping, generalisation, and trend analysis are applied to identify the key drivers of employer attractiveness and the barriers faced by local organisations. International conceptual frameworks are then compared with the national context in order to develop practical and context-sensitive recommendations.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Uzbekistan’s labour market combines abundant labour supply with a persistent skills quality gap. More than 60% of the population is under the age of 30, and approximately 700,000 young people enter the labour market each year. At the same time, higher education coverage among 18–23-year-olds has increased significantly, rising from about 8.3% in 2017 to 47.7% in the 2024/2025 academic year.

Meanwhile, the official unemployment rate declined to around 4.9% in the third quarter of 2025, while informal employment is estimated at approximately 40% of the workforce. Employers consistently report a shortage not of graduates, but of “market-ready” skills. This combination — a large number of candidates alongside intense competition for genuinely skilled and digitally literate specialists — creates precisely the environment in which employer branding becomes a decisive factor (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The demographic and talent-supply context of Uzbekistan: a large young population and rapidly expanding higher-education coverage create both opportunity and competition for skilled talent¹

¹ author’s development

Survey evidence indicates that employers are responding to this pressure. According to the EY Salary and Compensation Review 2024/2025, about 66% of surveyed companies planned to expand their workforce, while overall employee turnover rose by approximately 7% year-on-year.

Importantly, the response is shifting from pay alone towards the broader employee experience. Interest in well-being programmes increased by about 46%, the use of non-financial motivation tools grew by approximately 12%, and corporate meal programmes were offered by around 66% of firms (Figure 2).

Figure 2. HR and workforce signals in Uzbekistan, 2024/2025: hiring intentions remain strong, turnover is rising, and companies are investing more heavily in well-being and non-financial motivation²

These findings confirm that, in Uzbekistan as elsewhere, talent retention increasingly depends on the non-financial elements of the employee value proposition.

Synthesising the conceptual frameworks with these national patterns, the study identifies six dimensions of the employee value proposition that determine employer attractiveness, together with the branding levers an organisation can use to influence each of them (Table 1).

Table 1
Dimensions of the employee value proposition and corresponding employer-branding levers³

EVP dimension	What talents look for	Employer-branding lever
Compensation & rewards	Fair, transparent and competitive pay	Benchmarked pay bands and a clearly communicated total-rewards story
Career & development	Learning, mobility and visible growth paths	Mentoring, upskilling academies and internal promotion programmes
Work environment	Flexibility, well-being and psychological safety	Hybrid policies, well-being programmes and a healthy culture
Purpose & values	Meaningful work and shared values	An authentic mission narrative and credible ESG commitments
Leadership & trust	Respectful, competent management	Manager training and consistent, two-way communication
Employer reputation	Positive image among peers and online	Employee advocacy, reviews management and social-media presence

² author's development

³ Author's compilation based on recent employer-branding literature (Kucherov et al., 2023; Lassleben & Hofmann, 2023) and the CIPD employer-brand framework (2023).

The central finding is that an employer brand becomes a durable advantage only when the promise communicated externally corresponds to the experience delivered internally. In other words, the employer brand must be authentic.

The results suggest that the main constraint for Uzbek employers is not a lack of candidates, but a mismatch between what organisations offer and what skilled talent now expects. As remittance-driven labour migration remains substantial and global companies enter the market, local firms compete not only with one another but also with employers abroad. A coherent employer brand helps narrow this gap by clarifying the organisation's identity, differentiating it from competitors, and reducing both the cost and time of hiring.

Three practical implications follow from these findings. First, employer branding should begin internally: the most credible ambassadors of an employer brand are its own employees; therefore, investment in organisational culture, fair pay, and professional development must precede external promotion. Second, the employee value proposition should be segmented, since the priorities of an IT specialist, a graduate trainee, and an experienced manager differ, and a single undifferentiated message rarely resonates with all target groups. Third, the employer brand must be authentic and measurable: promises that are not fulfilled increase turnover instead of reducing it, while organisations that do not track engagement, turnover, and candidate experience cannot manage their employer brand effectively.

A limitation of this study is its reliance on secondary and survey data. Future research could test these relationships through firm-level empirical analysis in the Uzbek context.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Employer branding is no longer an optional refinement of HR practice, but a strategic response to the growing competition for talent. For Uzbekistan, whose young and growing population represents a genuine demographic dividend, the ability of employers to attract and retain skilled professionals will help determine whether this demographic potential translates into sustainable economic growth.

Becoming an employer of choice requires an authentic and clearly articulated employee value proposition, the consistent delivery of that promise across the entire employee lifecycle, and coordinated efforts among companies, educational institutions, and the state. Organisations that build such a reputation will secure not merely a stronger HR function, but a lasting competitive advantage in the economy of the twenty-first century.

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